

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES ON SUBSTANCE ABUSE AMONG THE ADOLESCENTS IN URBAN ZANZIBAR

Khadija Bakari Salum

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8406330>

Published Date: 04-October-2023

Abstract: The study adopted a cross sectional research design, both qualitative and quantitative data research designed was adopted in this study. A total of 71 respondents were involved in the study. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized in the study however, primary data was obtained through questionnaires, which was used to acquire quantitative data while qualitative data was obtained through a semi structured in-depth questionnaire. Quantitative data was analyzed through the SPSS and presented as frequencies, percentages, and correlation output on tables, and while qualitative data were sorted, placed under broader themes and presented as direct quotation upon content. Data findings reveal that over all, authoritative parenting does not influence drug use in Urban District Zanzibar, adolescents unlike neglectful parenting which positively influences drug use among adolescents. Sober houses also foster adolescent inmates in developing relapse preventing skills such as gratification delay, problem solving and emotional regulation among others. It is therefore recommended that among others, efforts should be targeted towards primary prevention in schools and sensitization of families on parenting. It is therefore recommended that among others, efforts should be targeted towards primary prevention in schools and sensitization of families on parenting.

Keywords: acquire quantitative data, influence drug, families on parenting.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Garcia *et al.*, (2020) parenting style is constellation of parent's attitudes and behaviors toward children and an emotional climate in which the parent's behavior is expressed. On the other hand, Patrick & O'Malley (2016) define substance abuse as the use of certain chemicals to produce pleasurable effects on the brain is referred to as drug misuse or substance abuse with more than 50% of substance abuse the beginning cases emerging during adolescence, adolescent substance use continues to be a major public health concern. Alcohol is the most often used substance among adolescents, followed by marijuana and cigarette smoking worldwide (Hamidullah *et al.*, 2020).

In the United States of America (USA), 2 million adolescents between the ages of 12 and 17 use drugs, with older adolescents and young adults accounting for 11% of drug-related overdose deaths (Volkow *et al.*, 2021). The use of cocaine, inhalants, heroin, methamphetamines, hallucinogens, or ecstasy was reported by 15% of high school students, while the misuse of prescription opioids was recorded by 14% of students. Youth who use drugs in injecting drugs run the danger of contracting HIV, and youth who use drugs generally are at risk of overdosing. Opioid use in youth is directly associated with sexual risk behavior (Ibid).

According to the World Drug Report (2021) and Jatau *et al.* (2021), Nigeria has much higher drug abuse prevalence than the global average at 14.4%. Drug abuse in Nigeria is a major public health concern. The report also highlights the negative effects that drug usage among young people, particularly adolescents, has on their health, families, communities, and their hopes for a career and higher education in Nigeria. A permissive parenting styles and alcohol drinking are risk factors for

alcohol among late adolescents and young adults (Floiland & Whitney, 2015). According to Kenya's national protocol for treating substance use disorders (2017), Substance abuse is on an increase in Kenya, especially among young people. According to recent figures, more than half of drug users are between the ages of 10 and 19. The majority of national research shows that marijuana, alcohol, and nicotine are the most widely consumed drugs among youths and adolescents. Due to Kenya's strategic location in East Africa and Nairobi's commercial center, there has been an increase in international narcotics trafficking, which has resulted in an increase in Injecting Drug Users (IDU). According to Kaggwa *et al.* (2022), 60–71% of Ugandan school-age children (12–24 years old) use addictive substances, namely alcohol (19.3%) and Kuber (4.4%). In a study of adolescents accessing the Makerere/Mulago Columbia Adolescent Health Clinic in Mulago, it was found that 15.6% of them abused at least one addictive substance, with alcohol dominating the group with 15.2% of use. Additionally, a Substance Use Disorder (SUD) is more likely to develop later in life if it begins earlier in life.

In Tanzania, the lifetime prevalence of substance abusers among school-age youth (aged 11 to 17) was 7%; the most common drugs taken were marijuana, amphetamines, and methamphetamine (3.1%), with alcohol coming in second at 4.5%. Cigarettes (15.5%), alcohol (9.2%), and marijuana (3%) were the most popular drugs used by school-age adolescents in the Kilimanjaro region. Tanzania has few studies on adolescent substance use. Therefore, there is a lack of evidence to support actions and policies (Francis *et al.*, 2015). There are many factors associated with adolescent drugs and alcohol experimentation and abuse such as personal values and personality traits. Parental styles are one of these aspects that is crucial. Demandingness (strictness, imposition, and parental firmness) and responsiveness are two key parenting practices that make up Maccoby and Martin's theoretical paradigm of parenting styles (warmth, acceptance, involvement). These aspects identify four parenting types authoritative, neglectful, indulgent, and authoritarian (Maccoby and Martin, 1983). But in my study I will discuss only neglectful and authoritative parenting styles.

The parenting style that combines intense control and affection is referred to as authoritative. Parents who are neglectful are loving yet don't make many demands (Maccoby & Martin, 1983). Although there is currently no known study linking parenting style to substance use among adolescents in Tanzania and specifically Zanzibar, studies conducted elsewhere, particularly in more developed countries have shown that adolescent are more likely to use drugs when they feel neglected by their parents (Holly & Shakya, 2012; Kabwama *et al.*, 2021). Teenagers are less likely to use drugs when they regard their parents as authoritative. Studies with Brazilian adolescents in particular revealed that using illicit drugs was linked to feeling unsupervised and never feeling understood by parents. In addition, parental supervision was a significant predictor for the reduction of polydrug use among teenagers. It has been suggested (Oesterle, *et al.*, 2012) that the authoritative parenting style can be seen as more protective and advantageous for the normal development of teenagers and is hence likely to prevent drug-related problems. Higher levels of self-esteem are shown by recent research on permissive parenting. A study on the authoritarian style revealed that it was linked to high levels of substance abuse and low levels of self-esteem (Valente *et al.*, 2019). In light of this context, this paper sought to answer the following questions

- i. How does authoritative parenting styles influencing adolescent on substance use in Urban Districts Zanzibar?
- ii. How does neglectful parenting style influencing adolescent on substance use in Urban District Zanzibar?

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study employed a cross-sectional research design under the mixed method approach. The design gave the researchers an opportunity to collect the two types of data concurrently

Target population and sampling techniques

The research target all the adolescent users currently obtaining treatment at Detroit sober house, Nyarugusu sober house and Free at last sober house. The choice of the target population is informed by the fact that the group of people has first-hand experiences with drug use and thus appropriately informed the study. The sample size of the study is 71. Both purposive and probability sampling techniques was applied in the selection of respondents (substance user and psychologist) that informed the study. The questionnaire was belonging to adolescent while interview focus on psychologist who have never used substance abuse. Also known as subjective sampling, purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where the researcher depends on their wise to choose variables for the sample population. Here, the whole sampling process depends on the researcher's judgment and knowledge of the context. If done right, purposive sampling

helps the researcher filter out irrelevant responses that do not fit into the context of the study (Lambart, 2020). A simple random sample is a subset of a statistical population in which each member of the subset has an equal probability of being chosen. A simple random sample is meant to be an unbiased representation of a group. (Foley, 2018). In this study, the Nyarugusu, Detroit and Free at last sober houses, all adolescent drug users were purposively selected and later, each had an equal chance to participate.

Instrumentation

The study used questionnaire to collect quantitative data this because questionnaire covers large population within short period of time while qualitative data were collected by using semi structure interview

Reliability and Data validity analysis

To establish reliability of the study, a pre-test was conducted at Serenity Center which has the same characteristics as the one where the study took place. Thirty (20) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Data obtained were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences research (SPSS) version 26 to determine reliability of the instrument. Cronbach's alpha was tasted and 0.70 value of point for a reliable tool therefore the questionnaire was reliable. Validity refers to the accuracy of a measure or whether the results really do represent what they are supposed to measure (Hamberstone & Heather, 2020). To ensure validity, the researcher administered questionnaires and made sure that a same question is phrased using different wordings and this enabled the researcher to get the important information. The instrument was considered valid since the CVI was above 0.6

Statistical Treatment of Data

Qualitative data was analyzed through thematic approach in a narration form. While Quantitative data, on the other hand, was analyzed through frequencies and percentages with the help of the SPSS.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure ethical research practice, the research ethics were noted quite well, the researcher sake permission from the responsible authorities. These include the ethic committee of the University of Iringa (UoI), Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar through authoritative bodies to conduct this research in Zanzibar such as the office of the Second Vice President, the office of Government Statistician, the three selected rehabilitation facilities, the 'Offices from all respective Districts in Zanzibar before data collection. Also in order to ensure that the culture norms of Zanzibar are not violated, the researcher looked for a signed consent of local leaders (*Shehas*). The researcher also respected autonomy and confidentiality of respondents. To avoid plagiarism, all authors whose literatures were reviewed were acknowledged through in-text citation and references.

The influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on substance abuse among adolescents in Urban Zanzibar

Table 1: The influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on substance abuse among adolescents in Urban Zanzibar

The following contributed to my addiction	A	N	D
There was little expression of love, warmth and affection in my family	56(78.6%)	3(4.2%)	12(17%)
My parent was too busy and was rarely involved in anything concerning me	50(70.4%)	2(2.8%)	19(26.8%)
My parents rarely monitored by activities	48(67.6%)	10(14.1%)	13(18.3%)
There were mental health problems in my family such as substance addiction	34(47.9%)	8(11.3%)	29(40.8%)
My parents rarely provided me with emotional support	57(80.2%)	1(1.4%)	13(18.3%)

Source: research data (2023) As depicted in Table 1 above, 56(78.6%) respondents agreed that there was little expression of love, warmth and affection in their family, 3(4.2%) respondents were neutral, while 12(17%) disagreed to the statement. These findings imply that respondents experienced limited love, warmth and affection from their parents, which is a risk factor for substance abuse since such family circumstances may push adolescents to seek a sense of belongingness outside the family, and perhaps in the wrong company such as drug users. The findings supported by one interview who said " my

parents are always busy with earning bread, they never even said I love to me and my siblings, I felt so bad about this “ Consistent with current study findings, Cluadia *et al* (2018) also investigated the effects of different types of Child Abuse and Neglect (CAN) according to levels of warmth in the parent-child relationship on common mental disorders (CMD) in adolescence Such as Substance Use Disorder. Results indicated that emotional abuse and neglect, physical abuse and neglect, and a low level of warmth in the parent-child relationship are important risk factors for CMD, particular addiction in adolescence. One interviewee had the following to say in support of the above findings.

As further revealed in Table 1 above, 50(70.4%) respondents agreed that their parent was too busy and was rarely involved in anything concerning them, 2(2.8%) were neutral, while 19(26.8%) disagreed with the statement. These findings imply that respondents’ parents were low in responsiveness and exercised minimal supervision of their children’s activities, which makes it difficult to intervene early enough, in case a child is using drugs. In support one interviewee had this to say “my parent has never had time for even once, they are always busy with working I thought ineed something to refresh my mind” in line with this finding, Berge (2016) examined the impact of parenting style on adolescent substance use. A cohort of 1268 adolescents (48% girls), aged 12–13 years at baseline, from 21 junior high schools was assessed in the first semester of junior high school, and then again in the last semester of the9th grade, 32 months later. Parenting style, operationalized as a fourfold classification of parenting styles, including established risk factors for adolescent substance use, were measured at baseline. Neglectful parenting style, featured by leaving adolescent activities unsupervised that is school progress, home activities and friends was associated with worse substance use outcomes across all substances.

Table 1 above further illustrates that, 34(47.9%) respondents agreed that there were mental health problems in my family such as substance abuse, statment,8(11.3%) neutral, while 29(40.8%) disagreed. Brewer (2017) perceptions of parenting behaviors among youth at a residential boot camp facility for at-risk adolescents, and to relate those perceptions to youths’ self-reported history of substance use. Data collection for this study was done via computerized surveys at the facility where the participants reside. A diverse sample of 255 adolescent boys (61.2% Caucasian, 30.2% African American, 0.4% American Indian, 4.3% multiracial, and 1.2% “Other” race/ethnicity) completed surveys asking about their use of drugs and their perceptions of how they were parented when living with their parents or guardians. . Also one interview had this to say “ I think I am an addict because I inherit it from my family, my mother sometimes yelling at me and said I am an drunk just like my grandfather. The results indicate that parental neglect was associated to drug abuse among adolescents

Lastly, table 1 reveals that 57(80.2%) respondents agreed that their parents rarely provided them with emotional support, 13(18.43%) disagreed while 1(1.4%) were neutral. This implies that parents are low in responsiveness, which is a significant quality of neglectful parenting, emotional neglect negatively impacts self-esteem, leading to higher possibilities of succumbing to peer pressure among adolescents, who often desire a sense of belongingness. In line to this findings, Tur (2019) assessed the relationships between substance use and parenting style and between substance use and perceived academic self-efficacy in early and middle adolescence. The results show that substance use and uninvolved parenting, particularly where parents were emotionally neglecting, are greater in middle adolescence than in early adolescence. The relationships between neglect and psychological control and substance use are moderated by academic self-efficacy, and the relationship between psychological control and substance use is mediated by academic self-efficacy in support one respondent narrated that. This findings also supported by one interviewee who said “ even the time that I was crying and feel down. My parents never gave me good words of comfort, I thought like I did not have parents”

The Influence of Authoritative Parenting style on substance abuse in Zanzibar

The first objective of this study was to determine the influence of authoritative parenting style on substance abuse among adolescents in Zanzibar and findings are presented in table 2 below.

Table 2: The Influence of Authoritative Parenting styles on substance abuse in Zanzibar

	A	N	D
Open parent-child communication was encouraged	8(11.2%)	9(12.7%)	54(76.1%)
Warmth and support were frequently displayed towards me as a child	16(22.6%)	12(16.9%)	43(60.5%)
My parent encouraged independence while placing appropriate limits on my behavior	12(16.9%)	3(4.2%)	56(78.9%)

My parent understood my feelings and encouraged me to share them	19(26.8%)	0(0.0%)	52(73.2%)
My views and opinions were strongly respected as a child	19(26.8%)	2(2.8%)	50(70.4%)
My parent allowed me to participate in establishing rules and regulation	28(39.4%)	0(0.0%)	43(60.6%)

Source: research data (2023)

As revealed in Table 2 above, 8(11.2%) respondents agreed that Open parent-child communication was encouraged by their parents while growing up, 54(76.1%) disagreed to this statement, 9(12.7%) were indifferent towards this statement. These findings imply that the majority of recovering addicts have been raised in families where communication was discouraged. In line with current study findings, Aslani *et al.* (2015), who investigated the relationship between permissive, authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles, emotional intelligence and religiosity with addiction potential among students in high schools of Ahvaz, also found that that authoritative parenting style, particularly in the aspect of healthy open communication in parent-child relationships, religiosity and emotional intelligence are effective in reducing addiction potential among the high schools students thus, concluding that among others, authoritative parenting was negatively associated with addiction among high school students.

As further revealed, 16(22.6%) respondents agreed that warmth's and support were frequently displayed towards them as children, 12(16.9%) Respondents were neutral, 43(60.5%) disagreed. These findings imply that the majority of respondents' parents didn't apply the authoritative parenting style while raising their children. This is because emotional responsiveness, which is a major feature of authoritative parenting was mainly lacking in their parenting style thus most, recovering addicts were emotionally neglected as children. Similarly, Karaer & Devrim (2019) investigated the influence of parental attitudes and emotional support on adolescents with Internet Addiction (IA). It was revealed that parents of adolescents with IA were more frequently inadequate in parenting and had less emotional availability. Adolescents with IA had less social support and more difficulty in identification of their feelings and emotion regulation. Lower parental supervision, higher alexithymia and the presence of an anxiety disorder are significant predictors of IA. Also the findings were supported by one interviewee "I never been given worth in my life, my parents were too harsh that I barely stayed close to them"

As demonstrated in Table 2 below, 19 (26.8%) respondents agreed that their views and opinions were strongly respected, 2(2.8%) were neutral, 50(70.4%) disagreed. one interviewee had this to say. Furthermore, one interviewee had this to say "my parents are always right. I had never said something and be listened, my views don't matter and therefore I chose to isolate myself" These findings further imply that parents had low responsiveness and high demandingness, which is a characteristic of authoritarian parenting and not authoritative. Consistent with current study findings, Luk *et al* (2010) investigated gender-specific variations in the associations between communication with father and mother, cigarette smoking, alcohol drinking and marijuana use in male and female adolescents. Logistic regression analyses controlling for race/ethnicity, family structure and socioeconomic status showed that the association of mother and father communication with adolescent substance use, particularly in the aspect of validating the opinions of adolescents, varied by substance and gender. Among sons, father's validation of views and opinions was protective against marijuana use and mother validation was protective against smoking.

3. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The following conclusions were reached in line with the research objectives. The current study concludes that there is a negative relationship between authoritative parenting style and substance use addiction among adolescents in Urban Zanzibar thus, authoritative parenting style does not positively influence the occurrence of substance addiction among adolescents in Zanzibar. This is because recovering addicts' parenting styles were lacking in the following key features of authoritative parenting namely, the majority of families lacked open parent-child communication, expressions of warmth, love and support were limited as perceived by respondents, a health balance of independence and appropriate limits were never ensured by parents, adolescents' views and opinions were generally overlooked, and finally respondent's parents excluded them from the creation and discussion of family rules and regulation. It is further concluded that neglectful

parenting has a positive influence on substance addiction among adolescents in Urban Zanzibar. This is because addicts confirmed that their parents mainly exercised neglectful parenting as evidenced by parental limited expression of warmth and love, limited time created by parents to interact and have conversations with adolescents, limited monitoring of adolescent's activities, and a history of substance use and addiction in the families of recovering addicts.

Recommendations

These findings hold practical implications for drug prevention efforts. Since parenting styles and social support are important predictors of adolescent drug abuse, the importance of integrating family-social support antidrug programs into adolescent prevention and intervention strategies should be considered by both sober houses, psychiatric and rehabilitation centers in Zanzibar. Since the scope of this study was limited to male adolescent drug addicts admitted to various sober houses in Urban Zanzibar, future studies should be conducted in communities and include female participants in order to bridge the knowledge gap regarding how parenting styles influence drug use among female adolescents in Zanzibar.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kagawa MM, Abaaty J, Alol E, Muwanguzi M, Najjuka SM, Favina A, et al. (2022). *Alcohol use and associated factors among adolescent boys and young men in Kampala*.
- [2] Berge J, Sundell K, Öjehagen A, et al. *Role of parenting styles in adolescent substance use: results from a Swedish longitudinal cohort*.
- [3] Brewer, B. R. (2017). How parenting style relates to adolescent substance abuse in an at-risk male population.
- [4] Froiland, J. M., & Whitney, N. (2015). Parenting style, gender, beer drinking and drinking problems of college students. *International journal of psychology: a biopsychosocial approach*, 2015, [Vol.] 16, p. 93-109.
- [5] Foley, B. (2018). The Methods of Probability Sampling. Probability Sampling vs. Non-Probability Sampling. Accessed on 23/07/2022 <https://www.surveygizmo.com/resources/blog/probability-sampling/>
- [6] Francis JM, Weiss HA, Mshana G, Baisley K. *The Epidemiology of Alcohol Use and Alcohol Use Disorders among Young People in Northern Tanzania*. 2015; 1–17. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0140041.
- [7] Garcia, O.F.; Serra, E.; Zacaes, J.J.; Calafat, A.; Garcia, F. *Alcohol use and abuse and motivations for drinking and non-drinking among Spanish adolescents: Do we know enough when we know parenting style? Psychol. Health* 2020, 35, 645–664
- [8] Cox, M.J.; Cai, L. A. H. M. S., Thorpe HHA, Frie JA, Mccurdy RD, Khokhar JY. *Adolescent substance use and the brain: behavioral, cognitive and neuroimaging correlates. Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*. 2020; 14 (298). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2020.00298> PMID: 32848673 Development, 37(4), 887-907.
- [9] Holly, B. Shakya, N. A. (2012). *Parental Influence on Substance Use in Adolescent Social Networks*. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med.*, 166(12), 1132–1139.
- [10] Jatau AI, Sha'aban A, Gulma KA, Shitu Z, Khalid GM, Isa A, Wada AS, Mustapha M. The
- [11] Burden of Drug Abuse in Nigeria: A Scoping Review of Epidemiological Studies and Drug Laws. *Public Health Rev.* 2021 Jan 29;42:1603960. doi: 10.3389/phrs.2021.1603960. PMID: 33796340; PMCID: PMC7904248
- [12] Humberstone, B. Heather, P. (2020). *Research Methods in Outdoor Studies*. Routledge. New York.
- [13] Kabwama, S. N., Matovu, J., Ssenkusu, J.M., Ssekamatte, T., & Wanyenze, R.K. (2021).
- [14] *styles in relation to alcohol abuse among the youths: A case study of Kibera slum, Kibra constituency* (Thesis, Strathmore University). Retrieved from <http://su-plus.strathmore.edu/handle/11071/6659>.
- [15] Karaer, Y., & Devrim A.B (2019). Parenting styles, perceived social support and emotion regulation in adolescents with internet addiction. *Comprehensive psychiatry*, 92, 22–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2019.03.003>, mn
- [16] Lambert, S. R. (2020). *Do MOOCs contribute to student equity and social inclusion? A systematic review 2014–18*. *Computers & Education*, 145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103693>. Oesterle, S., Hawkins, J.D., Steketee,

M., Jonkman, H., Brown, E.C., & Moll, M., (2012). *A cross-national comparison of risk and protective factors for adolescent drug use and delinquency in the United States and the Netherlands*. J.

- [17] Valente, D. A. (2021). House Manager Roles in Sober Living Houses. *Journal of substance use*, 26(2), 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14659891.2020.1789230>
- [18] Volkow ND, Han B, Einstein EB, Compton WM. *Prevalence of Substance Use Disorders by Time Since First Substance Use Among Young People in the US*. *JAMA Pediatr*. 2021; 175(6):640–643. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.6981
- [19] Claudia, E., Elgendy, R., Giantin, M., Dacasto, M., & Sissi, C. (2018). Whole-Transcriptome Profiling of Canine and Human in Vitro Models Exposed to a G-Quadruplex Binding Small Molecule. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 17107. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-35516-y>
- [20] Tur, J. A., & Bibiloni, M. D. M. (2019). Anthropometry, Body Composition and Resting Energy Expenditure in Human. *Nutrients*, 11(8), 1891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11081891>
- [21] Aslan, F., Özkan, H. B., & Sennaroğlu, L. (2015). Recent Rehabilitation Experience with Pediatric ABI Users. *The journal of international advanced otology*, 11(2), 110–113. <https://doi.org/10.5152/iao.2015.915>
- [22] Oesterle, S., Hawkins, J.D., Steketee, M., Jonkman, H., Brown, E.C., & Moll, M., (2012). *A cross-national comparison of risk and protective factors for adolescent drug use and delinquency in the United States and the Netherlands*. J.
- [23] Patrick, M. E., & O'Malley, P. M. (2016). *The epidemiology of substance use among adolescents in the United States*. In the Oxford Handbook of Adolescent Substance Abuse. Maccoby, E. E.; Martin, J.A. (1983). *Socialization in the context of the family: Parent-child interaction*. In Handbook of Child Psychology: Socialization, Personality, and Social Development; Mussen, P.H., Hetherington, E.M., Eds.; Wiley: New York, NY, USA, 1983; Volume marijuana use by Chilean adolescents. *Subst. Abuse Rehabil*. 2011, 2011, 1–11.
- [24] World drugs reports. (2021). Clinical features, complications and treatment of rarer forms of maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY) - A review. *Journal of diabetes and its complications*, 35(1), 107640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2020.107640>
- [25] Kaggwa MM, Abaatyo J, Alol E, Muwanguzi M, Najjuka SM, Favina A, et al. (2022). *Alcohol use and associated factors among adolescent boys and young men in Kampala*.
- [26] Luk, K. D. Kamath, V., Avadhani, A., & Rajasekaran, S. (2010). Cervical laminoplasty. *European Spine Journal: official Publication of the European Spine Society , the European Spinal Deformity society, and the European Section of the Cervical Spine Research Society*, 19(2), 347-348 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00586-010-1314-0>